

KINEMATIC DESIGN OF WEAVING MACHINE BEAT MECHANISM IN MSC ADAMS/VIEW SOFTWARE

¹Khalimov Kh., ²Pirnazarov A.U., ³Muradov A.A.

¹Master's student

²DSc

³Associate professor

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Abstract. *The movement of mechanisms depends on the ability of the link in it to move, and it performs work in a certain order. Mechanisms are assembled from certain kinematic schemes and designed to fulfill the desired law of motion, but it is impossible to create a mechanism that works precisely at once. Therefore, the task of determining the main kinematic characteristics of the mechanisms closer to the given conditions is set before the engineer-designer [1]. The main problem of kinematics of mechanisms is to determine the position, speed and acceleration of working links, sometimes the position, speed and acceleration of all intermediate links are checked in relation to the working link.*

Although the graphic method, which is widely used in the kinematic design of mechanisms, is a little faster, it limits the achievement of high-precision results due to the fact that drawing errors have a critical effect on the final result. It should be noted that the speed and acceleration of the mechanism links are determined graphically for only one position of the curve ship. For the remaining cases of the curved ship, it is necessary to draw separate drawings for each case of the curved ship to determine the velocities and accelerations of the connected links. Analytical analysis is useful in this case.

Keywords: *mathematical models, virtual prototypes, kinematic characteristics, velocities and accelerations of the connected links.*

THEORETICAL STUDIES.

The use of the analytical method is convenient in using modern computer programs and has the advantage of high accuracy [2,3,4]. In addition, it is easy to introduce and analyze mathematical models to the designed mechanisms in automatic design systems, and it is also possible to optimize the geometric parameters of the mechanism links.

The MSC Adams/View program allows engineers to simulate virtual prototypes of mechanical systems based on mathematical and physical laws and to conduct experiments while saving the necessary time and costs [5,6,7]. A multi-link dynamic system (KZD) is a set of rigid parts connected to each other by joints limiting their relative movement. Analyzing how mechanism links act under the influence of forces using the KZD system is called dynamic analysis. Studying the problem from the reverse, that is, studying what forces are needed to move the mechanical system in a certain way, is called inverse dynamic analysis. It is very important to analyze the movement. Because it is necessary to improve technological machines as a result of organizing connections between the construction of moving parts and the technological process [8]. Dynamic analysis of complex mechanical systems solves design problems that need to be solved by production. Dynamic and kinematic analyzes in an automatic design system allow for rapid evaluation and improvement of structures with critical features such as safety and comfort, and troubleshooting. MSC Adams/View includes a rich and easy-to-use interface for solutions for

kinematic and dynamic analysis and a wide range of functions for multi-link and mass system dynamic simulation.

MSC Adams/View software is used for many types of analysis:

- Tension analysis
- Vibration analysis
- Mechanical system analyses
- Kinematics analyses
- Analysis of friction in pairs
- Durability and expiration date analysis
- Calculation of fracture or fatigue

PRACTICAL RESEARCH

The design of the four-link batan mechanism in the MSC Adams/View program allows to obtain high-precision results while reducing time consumption.

Figure 1. Four-link mechanism diagram and MSC Adams/View model

First, MSC Adams/View is started and a model file is created. In this case, it is necessary to pay attention to the selected coordinate system and measurement units, and take into account that $\omega_0 = 10 \text{ rad/s}$. It is required to determine ω_{AB} and ω_{BC} .

Figure 2. Selection of coordinates and measurement system in MSC Adams/View program
Markers are created to mark base points in the selected coordinate system.

Figure 3. Creating markers

Mechanism links and joints are created on Markers.

Figure 4. Creating joints on markers

For the purpose of kinematic analysis of the created four-link mechanism, movement is given and simulated based on the given speed values.

Figure 5. Movement and simulation of joints

It is possible to get simulation results in graphic form or numerical values.

Figure 6. Graphic view of the simulation result

The result of MSC Adams/View is as follows:

X:	Y:
0.0	0.25
X:	Y:
0.0	0.5833

Analytical analysis of this four-link mechanism is as follows:

$$\bar{v}_A = \bar{v}_B + \bar{v}_{A/B}$$

$$\bar{v}_A = \bar{\omega}_{AO} \cdot \bar{r}_{AO} = 10\bar{k} \cdot (-0.06\bar{i} + 0.08\bar{j}) = -0.6\bar{i} - 0.8\bar{j}$$

$$\bar{v}_B = \bar{\omega}_{BC} \cdot \bar{r}_{BC} = \bar{\omega}_{BC}\bar{k} \cdot 0.18\bar{j} = -0.18\bar{\omega}_{BC}\bar{i}$$

$$\bar{v}_{A/B} = \bar{\omega}_{AB} \cdot \bar{r}_{A/B} = \bar{\omega}_{AB}\bar{k} \cdot (-0.24\bar{i} + 0.1\bar{j}) = -0.24\bar{\omega}_{AB}\bar{i} + 0.1\bar{\omega}_{AB}\bar{j} = -0.6\bar{i} - 0.8\bar{j} = -0.18\bar{\omega}_{BC}\bar{i} - 0.24\bar{\omega}_{AB}\bar{i} + 0.1\bar{\omega}_{AB}\bar{j}$$

$$\bar{\omega}_{AB} = \frac{0.6}{0.24} = 2.5 \text{ rad/s}$$

$$\bar{\omega}_{AB} = 5.83\text{k rad/s}$$

$$\bar{\omega}_{AB} = 2.5\text{k rad/s}$$

CONCLUSION

From the results of the obtained analysis and automatic design system, it can be seen that the kinematic analysis performed in the MSC Adams/View program is calculated with high accuracy and presented graphically.

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